

ECONOMIC EVALUATION OF NIGERIA'S TRANSPORTATION OF NATURAL GAS: THE AJAOKUTA, ABUJA, KADUNA AND KANO GAS PIPELINE PROJECT

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ABSTRACT

The economic viability of the abundant natural gas reserves in Nigeria and its transportation infrastructure is significant for improving energy supply, distribution, attracts huge industrial development, and guaranteeing energy security. Although, currently there is an inefficient natural gas development infrastructure, which has restricted the domestic utilization of gas in the gas rich nation. This paper presents a painstaking economic assessment of Nigeria's strategic Ajaokuta-Abuja-Kaduna-Kano (AKK) Gas Pipeline Project, a foundation project aimed at expanding natural gas infrastructure and driving socio economic development. The gas pipeline project is designed to cover a distance of 614-kilometer with a 40-inch diameter, configured to transport 3.5 billion cubic feet of natural gas (Bcf/d) from the Niger Delta to northern Region to boost power supply and industrial development along its route. The paper utilizes an advance economic analysis model, engineering design software, integrating Internal Rate of Return (IRR), Net Present Value (NPV), and Payback Period (PBP) in evaluate the profitability and long-term sustainability of the AKK gas pipeline project. The model utilizes sensitivity analysis, capital investment, operational costs, revenue forecasts, and risk-adjusted discount rates in conducting the evaluation and demand variations on profitability. Results shows that the AKK project proves a positive NPV and an IRR. Indicating that it is a potential profitable project. The research in addition explains the project's ability to generate key economic profits. The results are expected to serve as a tool for stakeholders, policymakers, and investors in making knowledgeable decisions that will bolster the country's natural gas utilization and contribute to sustainable economic growth.

KEY WORD: Natural Gas, Transportation, AKK Pipeline, Economic Evaluation

INTRODUCTION

Nigeria is the largest holder of natural gas proven reserves in Africa and the ninth largest holder in the world. Nigeria produced 1.2 trillion cubic feet (Tcf) of dry natural gas in 2012 and a reserve of an estimated 187 trillion cubic feet (Tcf) as of January 2013, ranking it as the world's 25th largest natural gas producer. Natural gas production is restricted by the lack of infrastructure to monetize natural gas that is currently being flared. (U.S energy information administration, Nigeria DEC,31 2013). Nigeria exports to mainly Asia, Europe, and the America of which is being threatened today. This is as a result of the shale gas discovery in the United States which positions the United States as a prominent gas exporter at about 2020. Although the country's presence in energy-hungry Asia has been growing in recent times, it is now being threatened by the increasing LNG export potential of the US and East Africa, as well as Singapore's aspiration to become the region's LNG trading hub. For the first time in more than 10 years the United States did not import any natural gas from Nigeria in 2012. As a result of rising shale gas production, it is projected that the US would become a net exporter of natural gas in the year 2030. This would lead to LNG supply abundance in the market and a likely decline in LNG delivery price to Asia and Europe, main destinations of Nigeria's LNG. (Whither Nigeria's global LNG market share Business Day). Apart from the risk from the US and Singapore, analysts believe that East Africa's immediacy to Asia is likely to stand it in good stead for LNG exports.

The outlook of Tanzania and Mozambique becoming LNG exporting nations is expected to present an authentic option for Asian buyers because of the shorter distance compared to Nigeria. East

Africa, in particular Mozambique, could be a new hotspot in LNG exports due to its recent large offshore discoveries, according to the British maritime classification society, Lloyd's Register, in its 'Global Marine Trends 2030' report. This will eventually reduce the income generated by the LNG business in the long run and hence leaving the company with limited options. Increasing the contract of long-term duration to over 25 years of LNG supply to demanding countries. Focusing on spot cargoes as an LNG spot and short-term market, procuring an approach for the domestic utilization of natural gas Hassan, M. M., & Garba, A. (2022). Natural gas has great importance for transportation, industrial, commercial, and domestic usage. NS Energy. (2020). To achieve this, new policies have to be made, a good pipeline network and storage facilities have to be installed and the diversification of natural gas has to be implemented as these are some of the objectives of the PIB bill. The study seeks an alternative for profit maximization for the nation through domestic utilization of its natural gas by improvising a prediction Model. To determine the pressure drops and compressor stations that can be situated in the pipeline network for the Niger Delta to Northern Nigeria. To determine the return on investment (ROI) for domestic transportation, to determine the turbulence kinetic energy and shear wall stress of the pipe. This paper covers AKK GAS PROJECT, using the chemical composition of the natural gas, the cost of laying the pipelines will be actualized as a function of previously played pipes, and the costs involved from us pipeline study due to the inaccuracy in Nigeria's data. Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation. (2024, June 21).

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

A. Early developments in oil and gas discovery in Nigeria

In 1908, a German unit, the Nigerian Bitumen Corporation (NBC), started oil exploration activities in Nigeria, particularly the Araromi area, in the Western part of the country. The pioneering work ended unexpectedly due to the First World War in 1914 (www.pengassan.org). Oil landscape work resumed in 1937; this time Shell D'Arcy (the forerunner of Shell Petroleum Development Company of Nigeria) was awarded the sole concessionary privileges covering the whole province of Nigeria. The Second World War interrupted the work hence in 1947 they resumed effort. This time an investment of over N30 million put in place which led to the first commercial discovery in 1956 at Oloibiri in the Niger Delta (<http://news.bbc.co.uk>). A good number of the international oil companies started their operation in Nigeria Oil industry in 1961, such as: Mobil, Agip, Safrap (then Elf, Total-fina Elf and now Total Exploration and Production), Tenneco and Amoseas (Texaco and Chevron respectively) to join the exploration work in offshore and onshore. The annexe of the concessionary rights previously a monopoly of Shell, to the greenhorns paved the way for the improvement. The goal of federal government was to speed up the exploration and production of Petroleum (www.pengassan.org).

Even now more companies, both foreign and indigenous have won concessionary rights and are producing. Actual oil production and export from the Oloibiri field in present day Bayelsa State commenced in 1958 with an initial production rate of 5,100 barrels of crude oil per day (www.nnpcgroup.com). The production rose to 2.0 million barrels per day in 1972 and a peaking at 2.4 million barrels per day in 1979. (www.lubconinternational.com). For the gas industry, Nigeria is endowed with abundant natural gas resources, which is reported to be in excess of the nation's proven crude oil reserve. More so, the gas was discovered during the search for crude oil, as no intentional effort had been made to search for natural gas subsequently. The current reserved estimate of the Nigerian gas is over 182 trillion cubic feet, with about 50/50 distribution ratio between Associated Gas (AG) and Non-Associated Gas (NAG). Only a small fraction of this

quantity is currently being utilized. (www.napims.com). A large portion (about 63%) of the AG produced during the production of crude oil is currently being flared. Even then this is a considerable improvement of between 7% - 17% from what it used to be three years ago, when it flared between 70% to 80%. In order to diversify its revenue base and reduce the huge wastage of valuable resource as well as the degradation of the environment as a result of flaring, the Nigerian Government, through the NNPC, is vigorously pursuing a number of natural gas utilization projects with its joint venture partners whereby associated gas would be harnessed to achieve these objectives. (www.napims.com). The Nigerian LNG project is being implemented in phases with an initial production from two trains. The plant is situated at Bonny Island. The bulk of the gas for base project is mainly NAG supplied from the following gas supplier fields: SPDC – SOKU; NAOC – OBIAFU OBIKROM; EPNL – OBITE. The bulk of gas for train three will contain more of associated gas from which both LNG and LPG will be produced. The Gas Supply Contract Quantities will have the joint venture supplying a total of 302.17 billion standard cubic metres (BSCM) of feed-gas required for the NLNG's three trains. The feed-gas for the three trains of which is now six trains will be a combination of associated and non-associated gas. When NLNG's train three becomes fully operational, a total of about 41.83 million standard cubic metres will be required by the plant daily. (www.nipco.gov.ng)

B. Diversification of Gas

The technological advances and generational leap is advancing from oil to gas. The world's largest energy reserves are seen as gas. It is cheaper, more environmentally friendly and is been applied in various sectors. Domestically, natural gas is used mainly in heating homes. In temperate regions like Nigeria, natural gas can be used as a source of energy in cooking though it comes mainly in the form of Liquefied petroleum gas (LPG). Commercially, natural gas is used in offices and complexes for heating purposes but majorly it is used for power generation. Nigeria produces only 4200 MW of which can satisfy only about 40% of the Nigerians population (www.nigeriapowerreform.org). Great opportunities can be seen here as private investors can loom in here for power generation, gas production and transportation, and support features throughout the value chain as Nigeria expects to meet up a target of about 40,000MW by the year 2020 (3rd international downstream conference, 2014). Industrially, natural gas has been implemented in the production of several products. In Nigeria, the large petrochemical industries are located at the Eleme LGA of which are Eleme petrochemicals which specializes in different plastic productions, Notore (Former NAFCON) specializes in urea formaldehyde fertilizer production and intels. They contribute in principle to the Nigerians GDP.

The feedstocks vary from olefins, natural gas, and gas to liquids (GTL-condensates) and petroleum products. The highly demanding sector is transportation. The growing demand for energy all around the world as gas is being transported in pipelines and through liquefied natural gas (LNG) in cargo ships. Since natural gas is cleaner it is now being applied and tailored as compressed natural gas (CNG) in vehicles through retrofitting. Cars now run in gas and PMS in Benin City and parts of Port Harcourt in Nigeria (total energy support, 2014) as it is seen to increase in the next coming year. Reports have it that gas is more economical, less issues, less noise and flexible to use. Since the Nigerian energy reserves are seen as pockets of oil fields in an ocean of gas, it is advisable that Nigeria makes use of its gas, reduce flaring and diversify its gas to meet the current energy demand through the various sectors.

C. Chronological realizations on transporting natural gas.

The storage of gas has posed numerous difficulties and so needs to be transported instantaneously to its destination after production from a reservoir (Cranmore and Stanton, 2000a). There exist a number of choices for transporting natural gas from oil and gas fields or facilities to market (Rojey *et al.*, 1997; Thomas and Dawe, 2003). These include pipelines, liquefied natural gas (LNG), compressed natural gas (CNG), gas to solids (GTS), i.e., hydrates. The following subdivision examines some of these technical methods by which natural gas energy can be transported and covers many of the essential points needed to enter the discussion. (Saeid Mokhatab *et al.*, 2006).

i. Pipelines

Pipelines are a very suitable method of transport but are not flexible as the gas will leave the source and arrive at its (one) destination (Cranmore and Stanton, 2000b). If the pipeline has to be shut down, the production and receiving facilities also have to be shut down because gas cannot be readily stored, except perhaps by increasing the pipeline pressure by some percentage. An average, over 12,000 miles per year of new gas pipelines have been completed over the last decade most are transnational. If political stability can be guaranteed, pipelines may be able to provide a long-term solution for transportation. An example of this approach is a proposed deep-water pipeline from Oman to India (EIA, 2002). However, the cost of building such a pipeline remains unclear. Subsea lines over 2000 miles have, until recently, been regarded as uneconomic because of the subsea terrain making pipeline installation and maintenance expensive and any recompression along the route difficult. these pipelines can become effective only if technical and economic hurdles can be overcome.

ii. Liquefied Natural Gas (LNG)

Liquefied natural gas technology has been proven to be successful since the mid-1970s. LNG is the liquid form of natural gas. Gas cooled to approximately -162°C liquefies and has a volume approximately 1/600 that of gas at room temperature. However, facilities for liquefying natural gas require multifaceted machinery with moving parts and special refrigerated ships for transporting the liquefied natural gas to market (Cranmore and Stanton, 2000b). The cost of building a liquefied natural gas plant have lowered since the mid-1980s because of significantly improved thermodynamic efficiencies, making liquefied natural gas a major gas export method worldwide, and many plants are being extended or new ones are being built in the world. Large cryogenic tanks are needed to store up the liquefied natural gas; typically, these may be 70 m in diameter, 45 m high, and hold over 100,000 m³ of liquefied natural gas. At the consumer end, an infrastructure for handling the reprocessing of vast quantities of natural gas from LNG is required, which is also expensive and vulnerable to sabotage. Oyeyemi, T. (2024, The current largest specially built refrigerated tankers can carry 135,000 m³ of liquefied natural gas, equivalent to 2.86 billion scf of gas, but are very expensive.

D. Compressed Natural Gas (CNG)

Gas can be transported in containers at high pressures, typically 1800 psig for a rich gas (significant amounts of ethane, propane, etc.) to roughly 3600 psig for a lean gas (mainly methane). Gas at these pressures is termed *compressed natural gas*. Compressed natural gas is used in some countries for vehicular transport as an alternative to conventional fuels (gasoline or diesel). The filling stations can be supplied by pipeline gas, but the compressors needed to get the gas to 3000 psig can be expensive to purchase, maintain, and operate. An alternative approach has dedicated transport ships carrying straight long, large-diameter pipes in an insulated cold storage cargo

package. The gas has to be dried, compressed, and chilled for storage onboard. By careful control of temperature, more gas should be transported in any ship of a given payload capacity, subject to volume limitation and amount and weight of material of the pipe (pressure and safety considerations).

METHODOLOGY

The methods follow a series of data collection, statistical analysis and simulations. The composition of Nigeria’s natural gas using the liquid gas chromatography (GC) respectively. Determining the pressure losses along the pipeline network and range for compressor stations. Using the Finite element Analysis (FEA) to determine the pressure distribution of the pipeline through computational fluid dynamics (CFD). Using statistical packages to predict the future of the AKK gas pipeline project profit maximization and cost for laying the pipelines. Using ASPEN packages to determine the capacities for gas diversification. The research employs an advanced economic analysis model, integrating Net Present Value (NPV), Internal Rate of Return (IRR), and Payback Period (PBP) calculations to evaluate the profitability and long-term sustainability of the project. The model considers multiple economic factors, including capital investment, operational costs, revenue forecasts, and risk-adjusted discount rates. Sensitivity analysis was conducted to assess the impact of fluctuations in gas prices, project costs, and demand variations on project profitability. The paper further explains the pipeline's ability to generate major economic benefits, such as job creation, enhanced industrialization, and regional energy security. The strategic role of the AKK pipeline in connecting previously underserved regions and stimulating socio-economic development is also underscored. Additionally, the project’s alignment with Nigeria’s National Gas Expansion Program (NGEP) and the government’s broader energy transition agenda is critically examined.

A. Description of natural gas characterization

The gas collected for the achievement of this project is from an associated well in Bonny field in which can be described as a wet gas owing to the presence of condensable gases contained in the Natural Gas stream. The gas compositions were gotten through the use of a gas chromatography in which the various percentages of the constituents of the gas were gotten. Below is a table showing the different compositions of Natural gas acquired from the bonny associated wells.

Table 1- Natural Gas composition form an Associated well (Prof. Iyagba, 2014)

COMPONENTS	MOLE FRACTION
Methane	0.8339
Ethane	0.0706
Propane	0.0395
i-Butane	0.0078
n-Butane	0.0115
i-Pentane	0.0038
n-Pentane	0.0031
n-Hexane	0.0031
n-Heptane	0.0023
n-Octane	0.0008
n-Nonane	0.0001
n-Decane	0.0001

CO2	0.0143
Nitrogen	0.0091
Total	1.0000

B. Geographical locale of AKKP

AKKP DISCRPTION

This study presents an in-depth economic evaluation of Nigeria’s strategic Ajaokuta-Abuja-Kaduna-Kano (AKK) Gas Pipeline Project, a cornerstone initiative aimed at expanding the domestic natural gas supply network and driving economic diversification. The AKK pipeline is a 614-kilometer, 40-inch diameter pipeline designed to transport up to 3.5 billion cubic feet of natural gas per day (Bcf/d) from the southern region to key northern markets, supporting power generation and industrial activities along its route.

C. Proposed AKK natural gas pipeline transmission

i. Pipeline parameters and Pressure drop models.

The transmission of fluids through pipelines requires many considerations in terms of material usage, process variables (which explicitly define the operating conditions of the fluid), the design and the topographical setting of the route. The pipeline material used for this project is *carbon steel* because of its accessibility, cost, and coating options. For a 24inch pipeline, the outside diameter is 610mm, having a thickness of 6.35mm according to the ASME B36.10M19M-2004. Below is a table of different pipe sizes:

Table 2. Schedule of different pipe sizes

S/N	SIZE(INCHES)	24”	28”	36”	48”
1	Outside Diameter (millimetres) (OD)	610	711	914	1219.2
2	Inside Diameter (millimetres) (ID)	597.30	695.16	898.14	1199.10
3	Thickness (millimetres)	6.35	7.92	7.92	10.05

The relationships used in the design of the pipeline are as follows:

$$A = \frac{\pi(D_i)^2}{4} \quad (1).$$

Where A =Cross section of the pipeline

D_i= Inside Diameter of the pipeline

The gas is expected to have a certain flow rate which is most times based on the supply of gas (scf) per day. The relationship between the flow rate and the cross section of the pipe helps in determining the velocity of the gas stream.

$$Q = Av \quad (2).$$

This can be modified as this

$$Q = \frac{\pi(D_i)^2}{4} v \quad (3).$$

The natural gas supplies to NLNG from the NNPC (APPENDIX 2), if **20-50%** of the gas supplies is diverted for domestic use and taking the highest observation then it means that we can decide that the gas flow rate to be transported will be **200m³/s** maximum and **30 m³/s** as minimum

neglecting year 2010, if that is to be considered. The velocity of fluid (especially gas) streams is of great importance as it transits from laminar to turbulent and as such the equation of state changes. A typical equation that can be used to describe this characteristic is the Real gas equation of state which is given by:

$$PV = ZnRT \quad (4).$$

Where P = the pressure of the fluid
V= volume of the gas
Z= the compressibility factor
R= Gas constant
N= no of moles of the gas
T= absolute temperature

The formation volume factor for gas is defined as the ratio of volume of 1 mol of the natural gas at a given pressure and temperature to the volume of 1 mole of gas at standard conditions (P_s and T_s). Using the real gas law and assuming that the Z factor at standard conditions is 1, the equation for formation volume factor (B_g) can be written as. (Saeid M et al, 2006)

$$B_g = 0.3507 \frac{ZT}{P} \quad (5.)$$

Where B_g is in m^3/Sm^3 , P is in KPa, and T is in $^{\circ}K$
This also influences the density of the natural gas, from equ (4.), the density of the stream can be modified to give

$$\rho_g = \frac{m}{v} = \frac{PM}{ZRT} \quad (6).$$

This can be modified more from the combination of equ (5.) and equ (6.) and also considering that the molecular weight of gas is the product of specific gravity and molecular weight of air and that the value of R is 8.314 in SI units, we can write the equation for density as

$$\rho_g = 3.49 \frac{P\gamma_g}{ZT} \quad (7).$$

where γ_g is the specific gravity of the natural gas. The density can also be written as

$$\rho_g = 1.224 \frac{\gamma_g}{B_g} \quad (8).$$

As the fluid flows inside the pipeline, it experiences a decrease in pressure owing to the rough surface of the pipeline. The pan Handel A, pan Handle B and the Weymouth equation helps in describing this effect. This depends strictly on the material of construction as the roughness factor varies with material types of the inner wall of the pipe, the diameter of the pipe, the length of pipe, compressibility factor, pressure and temperature of the fluid. But before this can be established the Reynolds's No, the friction factor and the relative roughness must be determined.

$$\text{Reynolds No, } Re = \frac{Du\rho}{\mu} \quad (9).$$

D: pipe ID (inside diameter), ft

u: fluid velocity, ft/sec

ρ : Fluid density, lb_m/ft³

μ : Fluid viscosity, lb_m/ft.sec

$$\text{Friction factor, (f):} \quad \frac{1}{\sqrt{f}} = 1.14 - 2 \log \left(e_D + \frac{21.25}{\text{Re}^{0.9}} \right) \quad (10).$$

$$\text{Where relative roughness:} \quad e_D = \frac{\varepsilon}{D} \quad (11).$$

ε = Roughness of the internal wall section, carbon steel (0.0046). The pan Handel B equation is stated as thus:

$$\left(\frac{1}{f} \right)^{0.5} = 16.7 \times \left(\frac{\gamma_g \times Q}{D} \right)^{0.01961} \quad (12).$$

$$Q = 737 \times \left(\frac{T_b}{p_b} \right)^{1.02} \times \left[\frac{p_1^2 - p_2^2}{\bar{Z} \times T \times L} \right]^{0.510} \times \left(\frac{1}{\gamma_g} \right)^{0.49011} \times D^{2.530} \quad (13).$$

The pan Handel A Equation.....

$$\frac{1}{f} = 52 \times \left(\frac{\gamma_g \times Q}{D} \right)^{0.1461} \quad (14).$$

$$Q = 435.87 \times \left(\frac{T_b}{p_b} \right)^{1.07881} \times \left[\frac{p_1^2 - p_2^2}{\bar{Z} \times T \times L} \right]^{0.5394} \times \left(\frac{1}{\gamma_g} \right)^{0.4604} \times D^{2.6182} \quad (15).$$

The Weymouth Equation.....

$$f = \frac{0.00235}{d^{0.33}} \quad (16).$$

$$K = 1.162 \times 10^7 \quad (17).$$

$$Q_h = 3.23 \times \frac{T_b}{p_b} \times \left[\frac{(p_1^2 - p_2^2) \times D^5}{\gamma_g \times \bar{Z} \times T \times f \times L} \right]^{0.5} \quad (18).$$

Where: Q_{SC} = flow rate, T_{SC} = Temp standard condition, P_1 = Pressure in, P_{SC} = Pressure standard condition, P_2 = Pressure out, K = Sand grain- roughness, L = length of pipe, D = diameter of the pipe, T_m = mean temperature of the gas, γ = specific gravity of the gas, Z_m = Mean compressibility factor, f = moody friction factor.

Using the pan Handel's A, B or Weymouth's equation, we can predict the operating inlet pressure that will be required having known the critical pressure and temperature of the stream and other parameters and determine whether or not how many compressor stations will be needed for the whole process. Different results will be gotten also as the diameter of the pipe changes. As the pressure changes, the compressibility factor will also decrease, hence for the natural gas. Offshore

Technology. (2021). The pressure and the compression fraction conjunction with the specific gravity will be related as thus. This was done setting the temperature at 45°C and flow rate of 200m³/s using the Peng-Robinson’s fluid package in Hysys. Following this approach, the Natural gas properties change spontaneously as the pressure vary.

Table 3: Relationship between pressure, compressibility and specific gravity

(P) (Kpa)	Compressibility(Z)	specific gravity (y)
7000	0.3363	0.674
6000	0.2888	0.672
5000	0.2411	0.6715
4000	0.1932	0.6702
3000	0.1452	0.6689
2000	0.097	0.6676
1000	0.0486	0.6663
500	0	0.6631
50	0	0.00541
10	0.9952	0.0003253
5	0.9976	0.0001623

ii. Pipeline route for Phase 1 and phase 2

The routes for installing the gas pipeline depends on so many factors of which will considerably determine the output technically and economically. The topography of the land, distance to cover, possible outlet terminals are determinant factors though they are aimed at the lowest cost. From EXCRAVOS to AKKP t in this thesis requires two different routes that can be feasible. The advantage is that it covers an area of potential buyers (Boda, Kpor Kpokiri, Ogu, agborehia) in the future thereby increasing the possibility of a higher utilization of the gas at a time.

Now that most of the parameters have been defined, if we apply the Pan Handel’s B equation in 18 and the value of 3500KPa (507.62psia) as the outlet pressure (critical pressure). The minimum inlet pressure can be defined as such.

$$P_1 = \sqrt{P_2^2 + \left(\frac{Q}{737} * \left(\frac{P_B}{T_B} \right)^{1.02} * \left(\frac{1}{D^{2.530}} \right) * \gamma^{0.4901} \right)^{\frac{1}{0.501}} * ZTL} \quad (19).$$

iii. De-Propanizer and De-Butanizer models

Before the natural gas is compressed and transported, it must be separated of its heavier hydrocarbon components. This helps in reducing the possibility of hydrate formation in the pipeline. This can be achieved by de-butanizing (removing C₄) and de-propanizing (removing c₃) the natural gas stream and as such decreasing the critical temperature and pressure between the liquid and vapour phase of the natural gas. This can be achieved through the use of a column or a heat exchanger. With the use of the column, there will be a better separation of butane and propane from the natural gas. Propane liquefies at -42.1° C and butane liquefies at -0.5° C

iv. Anticipated retail gas outlets

Due to the high population density in Port Harcourt. The likely utilization of the natural gas is on CNG production or Gas- Power project. According to a field trip at Total Energy support (17th

July, Rumukishiri, PH). The public in Port Harcourt are now becoming even more aware of CNG and how it can be used to fuel vehicles through retro-fitting, the potentiality of CNG is still waiting to be harnessed. Also, the gas can be used in fuelling power plants for electricity generation, as power supply is still a lingering problem in Nigeria. As the government of Nigeria advises Genco's to contribute into power as Nigeria sets to increase its generating capacity of 4200MW-40000MW by 2020, this stands as an opportunity for NLNG to sell of its gas. For the scope of this work, the retailing outlet will be focused on CNG production.

D. Safety Consideration

Installations Procedure and operation safety conditions in the process of laying a new pipeline, there are many processes that have to be carried out to complete the process. (Folga.S.M, 2007) This involves: Permits: Prior to construction, a proposed pipeline project must obtain numerous local, state, and federal permits and clearances. The permits address all natural resources — land, air, water, vegetation, and wildlife — as well as the interests of the general public. Survey and Staking: The first step of construction involves marking the limits of the approved work area (i.e., construction ROW boundaries, additional temporary workspace areas) and flagging the locations of approved access roads and foreign utility lines. Wetland boundaries and other environmentally sensitive areas also are marked or fenced for protection at this time. Before the pipeline trench is excavated, a survey crew stakes the centreline of the proposed trench. Clearing and Grading: Before clearing and grading activities are conducted, the landowners' fences (if any) are braced and cut, and temporary gates and fences are installed to contain livestock, if present. A clearing crew follows the fence crew and clears the work area of vegetation and obstacles (e.g., trees, logs, brush, rocks). Grading is conducted where necessary to provide a reasonably level work surface. Pipe Stringing, Bending, and Welding: Prior to or following trenching, sections of externally coated pipe up to 80 feet long (also referred to as "joints") are transported to the ROW by truck over public road networks and along authorized private access roads and placed, or "strung," along the trench in a continuous line. (Folga.S.M, 2007)

E. Econometrics

i. Estimating the CAPEX using multiple regressions model

In laying pipelines, an estimate of the capital costs needs to be acquired. The best approach to realizing this is to base your judgments in historical works. This consists of consulting previous pipelines that have been laid by determining the location, diameter of the pipe, distance covered, year of commissioning, material cost, labor cost, Misc costs, damages cost, topography and lots. Statisticians use different approaches in achieving a model that can co-relate all these parameters of which give the highest predictable model. The Least square method in achieving a regression can be used. Aid-Data. (2023).

$$Y = a_0 + b_1x_1 + b_2x_2 + b_3x_3 + \dots + b_n x_n \quad (20).$$

The least square can then be modified in determining the different un-known factors based on the degree of freedom of the problem and thus, it will be modified into a square matrix (m x n) format which will entail the use of other techniques in solving the unknowns which is basically cost.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sum y &= n + b_1x_1 + b_2x_2 + \dots\dots\dots b_n x_n \\
 x_1 \sum y &= x_1n + b_1x_1^2 + b_2x_1x_2 + \dots\dots\dots b_n x_1x_n \\
 x_2 \sum y &= x_2n + b_1x_1x_2 + b_2x_2^2 + \dots\dots\dots b_n x_2x_n \\
 &\cdot \\
 &\cdot \\
 &\cdot \\
 x_n \sum y &= x_n n + b_1x_nx_1 + b_2x_nx_2 + \dots\dots\dots b_n x_1x_n
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{21}$$

Where y= dependent factor which is usually cost, X= the different factors responsible for the dependent factor (size, distance....), n- No of observations, b= coefficient of regression. The main disadvantages of linear least squares are limitations in the shapes that linear models can assume over long ranges, possibly poor extrapolation properties, and sensitivity to outliers. Linear models with nonlinear terms in the predictor variables curve relatively slowly, so for inherently nonlinear processes it becomes increasingly difficult to find a linear model that fits the data well as the range of the data increases. As the explanatory variables become extreme, the outputs of the linear model will also always more extreme. (Nist .s, 2003). This means that linear models may not be effective for extrapolating the results of a process for which data cannot be collected in the region of interest. Of course, extrapolation is potentially dangerous regardless of the model type. Finally, while the method of least squares often gives optimal estimates of the unknown parameters, it is very sensitive to the presence of unusual data points in the data used to fit a model. One or two outliers can sometimes seriously skew the results of a least squares analysis. This makes model validation, especially with respect to outliers, critical to obtaining sound answers to the questions motivating the construction of the model. The Nonlinear least squares regression extends linear least squares regression for use with a much larger and more general class of functions. Almost any function that can be written in closed form can be incorporated in a nonlinear regression model. Unlike linear regression, there are very few limitations on the way parameters can be used in the functional part of a nonlinear regression model. The way in which the unknown parameters in the function are estimated, however, is conceptually the same as it is in linear least squares regression. It can be expressed in the form. (Nist .s, 2003)

$$y = (\vec{x}, \vec{\beta}) + \varepsilon \tag{22}.$$

Defining the prediction model for CAPEX and Profit (Time series)

Time series analysis accounts for the fact that data points taken over time may have an internal structure (such as autocorrelation, trend or seasonal variation) that should be accounted for. (Nist .s, 2003). Most of the historical trend of gas supply to the NLNG has been based on seasonal variation which was due to the increased utilization and the profitability of the company, hence to analysis futuristic purposes, we must acknowledge the trend that had occurred. Below is a graph of the Natural gas being supplied to the NLNG from NNPC. The average method is used when there are no trending factors and thus it explicitly produces equal weights on the differences

between the observed data. The weights are designated with the factor of $\frac{1}{N}$. Other methods include the single moving average and the center moving average.

$$\bar{x} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n x_i = \left(\frac{1}{n}\right)x_1 + \left(\frac{1}{n}\right)x_2 + \dots + \left(\frac{1}{n}\right)x_n \quad (23).$$

The exponential method is also sub-divided into the single, double and the triple (Holt-Winter's) exponential smoothing. These Exponential Smoothing assigns exponentially decreasing weights as the observation get older. In other words, recent observations are given relatively more weight in forecasting than the older observations. (Nist.s, 2003): Single Exponential Smoothing.

This smoothing scheme begins by setting S_2 to y_1 , where S_i stands for smoothed observation or EWMA, and y stands for the original observation. The subscripts refer to the time periods, 1, 2, ..., n . For the third period, $S_3 = \alpha y_2 + (1 - \alpha)S_2$; and so on. (Forecasting)

$$S_t = \alpha y_{t-1} + (1 - \alpha)S_{t-1} \quad 0 < \alpha \leq 1 \quad t \geq 3 \quad (24).$$

a. Double Exponential Smoothing

The Single Smoothing does not excel in following the data when there is a trend. This situation can be improved by the introduction of a second equation with a second constant, γ , which must be chosen in conjunction with α

$$\text{(Smoothing)} \quad S_t = \alpha \gamma_t + (1 - \alpha)(S_{t-1} + b_{t-1}) \quad (25).$$

$$\text{(Trending)} \quad b_t = \gamma(S_t - S_{t-1}) + (1 - \gamma)b_{t-1} \quad (26).$$

$$\text{(Forecasting)} \quad F_{t+m} = S_t + mb_t \quad (27.)$$

Where m = No of ahead period of forecasting. Triple Exponential Smoothing, This approach is used when the data shows trend and seasonality, then in this case double smoothing will not work. We now introduce a third equation to take care of seasonality (sometimes called periodicity). The resulting set of equations is called the "Holt-Winters" (HW) method after the names of the inventors. The basic equations for their method are given by (Nist .s, 2003):

$$\text{(Overall smoothing)} \quad S_t = \alpha \frac{y_t}{I_{t-L}} + (1 - \alpha)(S_{t-1} + b_{t-1}) \quad (28).$$

$$\text{(Trend smoothing)} \quad b_t = \gamma(S_t - S_{t-1}) + (1 - \gamma)b_{t-1} \quad (29).$$

$$\text{(Seasonal smoothing)} \quad I_t = \beta \frac{\gamma_1}{S_t} + (1 - \beta)I_{t-L} \quad (30).$$

$$\text{(FORCAST)} \quad F_{t+m} = (S_t + mb_t)I_{t-L+m} \quad (31).$$

Where, y is the observation, S is the smoothed observation, b is the trend factor, I is the seasonal index, F is the forecast at m periods ahead, t is an index denoting a time period, and α , β , γ are constants that must be estimated in such a way that the, MSE of the error is minimized. This is best left to a good software package. For this thesis, we shall employ the use of mini-tab, which defines α , β , γ as **0.2** as its default.

3.5.3. Defining Net present value (NPV) and the interest rate of the project

The Net present value assigns the value of an investment project found by adding the present value of expected future cash flows (F_v) and the cost (P_v) of the initial investment. It critically tells the worth of the same value of cost in the future, hence it operates with the no of years (n) and the interest rate (r). The interest rate is mostly determined by the banking sector. It is given by the equation:

$$F_v = P_v (1 + r)^n \quad (32.)$$

Using the aspen CAPITAL Estimator for determining the plant cost

Aspen Capital Cost Estimator, formerly known as Aspen K base, is a fully integrated, design, estimating, and scheduling system designed to help you evaluate the capital cost of process plants worldwide. Aspen Capital Cost Estimator uses the equipment models contained in the Icarus Evaluation Engine (IEE) – a knowledge base of design, cost, and scheduling data, methods, and models– to generate preliminary equipment designs and simulate vendor-costing procedures to develop detailed Engineering-Procurement-Construction (EPC) estimates. Volumetric models generate a costed, quantity takeoff for the bulk materials without using factors or user input. The volumetric models also produce the quantities of pipe, valves, concrete, steel, and instruments identified by the associated equipment or area. Components of each line of pipe and instrument loop are quantified and costed, enabling you to view and adjust construction tasks.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Gas Characterization

Natural Gas quality and measure

The gas characterization was done through the use of HYSYS (7.1) package. The components were defined as thus in table 3.1 and the fluid package used was the Peng-Robison. In the oil manager and environment tab, the assay data type was chromatography. The software now calculates the stream after all the components have been inputted based on molecular weights. The cut/blend cuts the stream into hypo-components. This provides the critical pressure and temperature at which the fluid needs to operate.

Fig. 1: Boiling point of the natural gas fractions with respect the mole %

From the diagram it shows that the highest critical pressure is 3400kpa, below it there would be formation of hydrates in the pipeline, the compressor needed should compensate for the pressure. The second figure depicts the maximum temperature needed of the gas in the pipeline which is about 175°C, this temperature is relatively high and so requires some separation to avoid hydrate formation during transportation.

Fig. 2

Fig. 3: A figure of the new critical pressure of the Natural Gas stream

The critical pressure is dictated as 3380KPa which can be tolerated to about 3335KPa before there will exist the presence of condensates in the gas stream. The temperature also is dictated as 65°C. This temperature is easier to maintain the pipeline as compared to the 150°C of the original feed.

Since the pipeline is to be buried then it means that the stream can be seen as isothermal in nature because of the insulating nature of the soil. To avoid any errors in the outlet temperature, it is safe for us to keep the pressure a bit high enough due to some factors that may want to take place. Using a pressure of 3450KPa as the outlet pressure can be a fastidious set point.

B. Technological perception of the Transportation system

i. Pressure drop analysis

The pressure drops as stated in chapter 3, using the pan Handel’s equation can hence be used in determining the least input pressure to achieve the pressure and temperature not going below the critical points. Recalling the pan Handel’s equation in equation (3.20), we can now make an estimate of the inlet pressure of the natural gas stream. Also using the properties of the natural gas stream after the separation process found in Appendix 1. (using the American system)

Table 4: Minimum inlet pressure to be applied to the pipelines of various diameters

p2	Q	PB	TB	D	S.G	Z	T	L	P1
3450	159940126	14.7	520	24	0.637	0.9427	609	26.7	3454.821
3450	159940126	14.7	520	36	0.637	0.9427	609	26.7	3450.623
3450	159940126	14.7	520	48	0.637	0.9427	609	26.7	3450.146
$p_1 = \sqrt{p_2^2 + \left(\frac{Q}{737} * \left(\frac{P_F}{T_F} \right)^{1.02} * \left(\frac{1}{D^{2.530}} \right) * \gamma^{0.4901} \right)^{\frac{1}{0.501}} * ZTL}$									

We can see that the pressure drop is very minimal and so if we use a compressor of 35.4bar, there will be no need to install compressor stations along the pipeline length between PH and Bonny city using a 24” pipe. Simulating the pipeline network using *pipe phase*, we can determine the pressure drop-distribution along the pipeline length. The thermodynamic property is displayed as such.

ii. Pressure and temperature variation along pipeline

As shown below, a pipeline network from bonny to PH for the diversification of its natural gas, is been set with the operating conditions of the pressure, temperature and flow rate of the inlet and outlet PIPE. Notwithstanding, the thermodynamic property used in pipe-phase is expected to simulate the pressure distribution as well as the temperature distribution along the pipeline due to the ambient temperature defined (26.7°C), the roughness of the pipe, the conductivity of the buried pipe in the soil and the pan Handel B model as it contributes to the flow. The network is as shown in the next figure below. The data can be seen in Appendix 8.

iii. Stress analysis of pipelines through Computational fluid dynamics

As the Natural Gas flows through the pipeline, the gas experiences a turbulent behavior which creates a turbulent kinetic energy. This energy exerts some stresses on the walls of the pipeline of which is to be analysis and calculated. The turbulent flow is based on the K-epsilon turbulent model which can be given as:

For turbulent kinetic energy

$$K \frac{\partial(\rho k)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(\rho k u_i)}{\partial x_i} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left[\frac{\mu_t}{\sigma_k} \frac{\partial k}{\partial x_j} \right] + 2\mu_t E_{ij} E_{ij} - \rho \varepsilon \quad (32.)$$

The model is interpreted as Rate of change of k + Transport of k by convection = Transport of k by diffusion + Rate of production of k - Rate of destruction of k, Where: u_i = velocity component in the corresponding direction, E_{ij} = component of rate of deformation, μ_t = eddy viscosity

$$\mu_t = \rho C_u \frac{K^2}{\varepsilon} \quad (33.)$$

The turbulent model requires so many iterations and was modelled using the Ansys multiphysics softer package. The computational fluid dynamics (CFD) fluent under the software was used to model and analyze the pipeline transport scheme.

- **The velocity magnitude**

Fig 4: velocity magnitude gradient along the pipeline

The velocity magnitude was calculated having a maximum value of $5.19 \times 10^2 \text{ m/s}$ and a minimum value of $5.15 \times 10^2 \text{ m/s}$. We can see that the velocity is maximum at the centre of the pipe, but the velocity gradually drops at the walls of the pipe due to friction. The turbulent kinetic energy, the turbulent kinetic energy increased significantly from $1 \text{ m}^2/\text{s}^2$ to $2.78 \times 10^2 \text{ m}^2/\text{s}^2$ along the pipe walls as this may be attributed to the randomness of the particles along the walls.

Fig. 5: Turbulent Kinetic Energy gradient along the pipeline

- Wall shear stress

C. Economic Analysis of the transport system

i. Capital cost of project phase 1 and 2

Based on the different phases of the project, as earlier discussed in chapter 3, estimating the capital cost of the project will have to be from past works that has been carried out in the past. The cost of such projects will have to be renewed from their past nature to the present state. That is where the net present value of the initial cost has to be simulated. The data consisting of the cost of laying pipelines in conjunction with the lengths involved and the diameter of the pipe was gotten from the *U.S pipeline cost study, 2008*. Given equation 3.32, the net present value of onshore projects conducted in the U.S with a discount rate of 5% (international monetary fund, 2014) from 2007 - 2015 (8 years) will be given as table 4.2 From this we can simply run a multiple regression from the data using the least square method in a statistical project (*minitab*) to acquire the *model*

ii. Profit Prediction using time series

Before we can start with the prediction of the profit margin of the project. We need to account for all the cost of the project. This involves the CAPEX and the OPEX of the entire project and the time for achieving the return on investment (ROI). The different cost to be accounted for involves the cost of laying the pipeline, the De-Propanizer and De-Butanizer plant, the CNG compressor station at the pipeline terminal and the operating cost (OPEX). The cost for installing the de-Butanizer and de-Propanizer plant as well as the CNG compressor plant can be viewed from the APPENDIX 5 which was analyzed using the Aspen Capital Cost Estimator where there were considerations for the design parameters, the piping's, the civil, structural, electrical, insulations, and painting descriptions and costs.

Table 4: Summary Costs for the CNG compressor station

Item	Material(USD)	Manpower(USD)	Manhours
Equipment&Setting	1591300.	20612.	693
Piping	84943.	36755.	1224
Civil	8343.	6785.	295

Structural Steel	0.	0.	0
Instrumentation	83022.	36337.	1232
Electrical	4885.	12240.	435
Insulation	12656.	8614.	402
Paint	1427.	3837.	181
Subtotal	1786576	125180	4462

Total material and manpower cost=USD 1911800.

The estimates for the De-Butanizer and Propanizer as well as the compressor station (\$364700 and \$1911800 respectively) were done with a 2008 solver engine and so we must get the future value to the year 2015. Using the NPV model and the other parameters as done previously in the chapters above, the future values for the projects will produce

- De-Butanizer and Propanizer cost: \$513169.52
- CNG Compressor station cost: \$2690094.59

Hence the total cost of this project if it is to be implemented in the year 2015 will be the addition of the **Cost of laying the pipelines (24")**, **De-Butanizer and Propanizer cost** and the **CNG Compressor station cost**. **This will give a sum total of:** Total Cost: 178128790 + 513169.52 + 2690094.59, Total cost: \$ **181332054.11/Yr**. The annual amounts are often estimated by a rough rule of thumb to be 5% of the total capital costs. (<http://www.mhnederlof.nl/economics.html>), Hence the operating cost per year will be: **OPEX = \$9066602.7055/Yr**, *At this charge and assuming the project takes one year to accomplish, then it means that returns will start at the year 2016, Overall cost of the project = CAPEX + OPEX (FOR 2015), Overall cost of the project = \$181332054.11 + \$9066602.7055, Overall cost of the project = \$ 190398656.8155 (For 2015), If we decide to use 20-50% utilization then our profit margin will be given as: Profit margin (1st year) : (Revenue – (CAPEX + OPEX)), Profit margin (other years) : (Revenue – OPEX), ROI : (Profit margin)_{n+1} – (Overall cost of the project)_n*

Considering the two figures above, the first figure depicts the Overall cost and the return on investments (ROI) along the years at a fixed price of N70 (\$0.423). There we see that the NLNG will make up for the cost of their investment at the year 2017 if they kick off by 2015. The interception between the Overall cost and the ROI curve falls on 2017 but if NLNGs to start with a price of N90(\$0.544) then it will take a much quicker time to have a return on their investments in the year 2016 as the second figure shows that. The other figure below shows a graph of the profit margin and the ROI, it explains that the accumulated ROI increases as the profit keeps coming until a time where there would be a reduction in the ROI. All the different sale prices and ROI shares this characteristic.

Fig 6: Plot of ROI against PROFIT between the year 2015-2020 at N70 (\$0.423)

From this figure, as the accumulated ROI reached 200 million dollars which ought to be around year 2018. It is advisable that the NLNG increase their sale price to increase their margin on the ROI that is if the competitors are not much (high supply). The same trend can be applied no matter what the level of gas utilization is subjected in carrying out the CNG project, as this helps to predict what year and sub-sequentially the exact period where the pricing should be adjusted for maximizing the returns on investments.

Regression Analysis: PROFIT versus Actual flow (m3/s), Overall cost (20% Utilization)

The regression equation is

$$\text{PROFIT} = - 8.61\text{E}+08 + 22424909 \text{ Actual flow (m3/s)} + 2.58 \text{ Overall cost}$$

Predictor	Coef	SE Coef	T	P
Constant	-860969578	362732210	-2.37	0.098
Actual flow (m3/s)	22424909	4312736	5.20	0.014
Overall cost	2.580	1.583	1.63	0.202

S = 54694613 R-Sq = 90.1% R-Sq(adj) = 83.5%

From the analysis, a prediction model relating the actual flow and the overall cost to actualize the profit for a 20% utilization and the price at N70 (\$0.423). The probability value of 0.098 is very close to the level of significance of 95% and a R² of 90.1% which proves stability.

CONCLUSION

The domestic transportation project via pipeline from bonny island to Port Harcourt can be seen as a viable suggestion to the topical challenges that is posed to the NLNG. It would take NLNG just one year to regain its investment in this project if they can completely and domestically utilize just 20% of the Gas stream supply being issued by the NNPC. This possibility is deemed with a pipeline diameter of 24” and a distance coverage of 27.6 miles. Using the Times series, the supply, profit and thus the ROI of the project was actualized till the year 2020 stipulating that the project starts and concludes at the year 2015(where all requirements for execution are being prepared) and

thus the revenue from the project commences. In this thesis, a model that can estimate the cost of laying a pipeline which includes all considerations to the laying project was generated for onshore conditions and offshore conditions having the diameter and the mileage as independent factors. The coefficient of determination of the model was also considerably high, giving a value of 71.8% and a p-value of 0.06 which is close to the percentage level of significance.

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